

Exploring Quantum Tonality

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Abstract. *The present article reports on a series of mathematical experiments in preparation of a composition-project, which is based on the dynamic behavior of a quantum model of C-Major tonality. The model itself is based on a re-interpretation of the empirical pitch class profiles of tonal attraction in C-Major in terms of the probability wave function of a one-dimensional stationary ground state solution of a perturbed quantum harmonic oscillator. The solutions to the associated time-dependent Schrödinger-equation associate time-developments with any given initial state. The time developments of coherent states are used to simulate quantum measurements for creating basic melodies and diminutions thereof. The time-developments of other initial states, such as deflections of the ground state and of the higher excited states are used to derive parameters for the creation of heterophonic textures, as well as for the control of rich continuous sound processes. The latter type of experiment does not rely on (the simulation) of quantum measurements, but takes instead direct advantage of the theoretical understanding of the time-developments without the loss of knowledge (as implied through the collapse of the wave function in the quantum measurement).*

1 Introduction: From C-Major to Quantum C-Major

The present paper is a synergy from two parallel strands of study, namely investigations into quantum models of tonal attraction [1, 2, 3], on the one hand and investigations into the automation of heterophonic textures in [4], on the other. The idea is to bring a more theoretical approach to the modelling of tonality in direct contact with a hands-on experimental musical approach to the sonification of one-dimensional quantum wave functions. While the sonification project was originally inspired by the tonality project, we return now with new ideas to the exploration of quantum tonality. This also includes experiments with a recent related approach to the synthesis of sounds (see [5]).

The concept of *quantum tonality* is based on a particular interpretation of the Krumhansl-Kessler pitch class profile for C-Major [6]. If the tonal attraction values for the pitch classes are aligned in fifth-order $G_b, D_b, A_b, \dots, C_\sharp, F_\sharp$ they can be well fitted with a Gaussian mixture model (GMM)

$$p(x) = \sum_{k=1}^N \alpha_k \rho(x - a_k) \quad (1)$$

with Gaussian kernel

$$\rho(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \frac{x^2}{\sigma^2}\right) \quad (2)$$

and mean values at C, G and E for $N = 3$ (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Fitting of the Krumhansl/Kessler pitch class profile for C-Major with a Gaussian mixture model (GMM)

We can then interpret the Gaussian mixture as the probability density function of the ground state of a perturbed harmonic oscillator [7, 8] with the double-well potential [9]

$$V(x) = V_0(x) + \frac{\sum_{kl} [(a_k - 3a_l)x + a_l(2a_l - a_k)] \alpha_k \alpha_l \rho(x - a_k) \rho(x - a_l)}{\sum_{kl} \alpha_k \alpha_l \rho(x - a_k) \rho(x - a_l)} \quad (3)$$

shown in Figure 2. Note, that $V_0(x)$ describes the quadratic potential of the pure quantum harmonic oscillator [10] with ground state energy

$$E_0 = \frac{1}{2\sigma^2}. \quad (4)$$

The mathematical details of the corresponding Hamilton operator, its associated Schrödinger equation and their solution eigenstates are comprehensively described in [3].

1.1 Initial States and Their Time Developments

We present several musical experiments on the basis of the dynamics of this quantum system. Each experiment starts with the preparation of a specific initial state and takes shape through the extraction of the parameters from

Figure 2: Musical interaction potential $V(x)$ for C-Major (solid) in comparison with the unperturbed potential of the quantum harmonic oscillator $V_0(x)$ (dashed).

its time development. At the first stage the term “experiment” is, in fact, meant to follow the role of position measurements in experimental quantum physics (see Section 2). At this state the theoretical knowledge is only used for a computational simulation of these measurements. At the other stages, however, we take advantage of the full knowledge of the Hilbert Space of wave functions and the action of the time evolution operator on any given initial state. We experiment with the following 3 types of wave functions in the role of initial states.

1. Single tones can be represented by narrow Gaussians centered at the given tone positions. In the dynamics of the unperturbed quantum harmonic oscillator deflections of the (Gaussian) ground state are known as *coherent states* and move along the x -axis like a classical pendulum. In our perturbed situation their time-development is considerably more complex.
2. In literal analogy to the coherent states we consider deflections of the Krumhansl-Kessler ground state. Note, that the ground state for this double-well potential is described by a bimodal probability density function here [9]. Further note, that a shift of the C-Major-ground state by a fifth in \sharp -ward direction may, of course, be modeled with its own Schrödinger-equation as a stationary ground state of G-major tonality. But alternatively, we consider it as an initial state within the dynamics of the quantum C-Major tonality. Then its non-stationary time development can be interpreted as a continuous modulation through fluctuating fuzzy tonalities. Wider deflections induce wider ranges of change, correspondingly. Figure 3 displays three selected states from the continuous time development. The positions at the underlying configuration space (fifth-width-axis) can be, on the one hand, interpreted as abstract tones and, on the other hand, also as locations of the different voices in an ensemble. Both possibilities can be used in combination and also separately. We use the time developments of the deflected ground state to create heterophonic textures (see Section 3). Thereby, we rely on the

Figure 3: Three successive states of the continuous time development of the deflected ground state by one fifth in \sharp -ward direction. This initial state is shown in the 1st frame. The contours of the colored shapes (in all three frames) represent the absolute values of the momentary wave function, the black lines show the corresponding probability density functions. The hue values in the colored shapes represent the complex phases.

unity of the wave-function as a whole to be a source for musical unity in the variety of the different voices.

3. The same procedure can be applied to deflections of the higher excited states. We use the time developments of deflected excited states to create dynamically evolving sound processes by controlling spectral components with their magnitude and phase parameters at different positions (see Section 4).

2 Plain Melody from Quantum Measurements

Suppose at time $t = 0$ we are given a coherent state, centered at a tone position x in the role of an antecedent state. What does it mean, to make a position measurement of its time development at some time point t ? In our model we assume that the traveling wave function collapses into an-

other coherent state y (as its consequent state). The probability for this outcome $x \rightsquigarrow y$ is given by the Hilbert space overlap of the antecedent's x time development at t and the consequent y in question. When we reduce the continuous space to a finite selection of 16 tones, we obtain a time-dependent continuous family of Markov-models. For each time point t we obtain a 16×16 -matrix of transition probabilities. Figure 4 visualizes three of these Markov models by means of contour plots.

Figure 4: Contour plots of the time-development of the Hilbert space overlaps in fifth-width space for antecedents (vertical) and consequents (horizontal) for three selected time points. The respective values are represented by varying degrees of brightness.

To perform these experiments interactively in real time in Max/MSP, the Markov matrices are pre-calculated

for a sufficiently fine time resolution. Once a transition $x \rightsquigarrow y$ is established (by a simulated measurement experiment), the *tone* at y becomes the new antecedent and the time counter starts again from $t = 0$. Apart from the main melody $x_1 \rightsquigarrow x_2 \rightsquigarrow \dots \rightsquigarrow x_n$ the momentary Markov model is being used to create little diminutions (ornamental melodies) until the next measurement is being performed interactively. With these diminutions we already cross the borderline between the fully forgetful experiment and the usage of our theoretical knowledge of the Hilbert space.

3 Heterophonic Textures

Although our time developments are continuous both in space and time, we reduce the continuous configuration space \mathbb{R} to the $n = 16$ tone locations. For every time point we thus consider n magnitudes and n phases for the individual tones. In each moment t the tones can be sorted by descending magnitude values (x_1, \dots, x_n) . The ordering allows the construction of a hierarchy like

$$\{x_1\} \subset \{x_1, x_2, x_3\} \subset \{x_1, \dots, x_7\} \subset \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$$

These hierarchies follow the constitution of tonal hierarchies as studied for example by Lerdahl [11]. x_1 is the current tonic, $\{x_1, x_2, x_3\}$ the current “triad”, and $\{x_1, \dots, x_7\}$ is the current diatonic scale (mode).

Initial musical motives are chosen at all hierarchical levels. They are chosen abstractly in terms of chord degree and scale degree sequences. In the time flow the tone-occupations of these hierarchical levels change and give rise to continuous (musical) modulations. Voices are also parameterized by selected positions. The specified motives are realized simultaneously in all voices, while the corresponding complex phases give rise to different rhythmical manifestations and the magnitudes to different event densities, articulations and dynamics. The resulting voices constitute similar, but yet considerably varied instances of the same motivic material, which we associate with the concept of *heterophonic texture*. The changes themselves are driven by the time development of the wave function and thereby have a unifying effect over the individual variations.

4 Continuous Sound Processes

A third type of experiment is dedicated to the creation of a continuously changing complex sound or sound mass. The following concrete example illustrates the overall idea. The sound is a superposition (additive synthesis) of $n = 16$ FM-modulated signals at (or in the neighborhood of) rising frequencies, such as

$$40., 60., 90., 135., \dots, 17515.8$$

FM-synthesis for each signal allows for a faithful sonification of the associated complex phase. To that end we express every phase with a superposition of three different FM-signals, whose relative impact is modulated by three

Figure 5: Dynamically changing tonal hierarchies for two different initial states; left: deflected ground state by one fifth; right: deflected ground state by three fifths (red: local tonic, red/blue: local triad, red/blue/yellow: local mode. The time flow is from bottom to top.

sine functions, which are displaced by offsets of $\frac{2\pi}{3}$ and $\frac{4\pi}{3}$, and which together add up to the constant function 1:

$$\frac{\sin(x) + 1}{3}, \frac{\sin(x + \frac{2\pi}{3}) + 1}{3}, \frac{\sin(x + \frac{4\pi}{3}) + 1}{3}.$$

Figure 6: Impact of each the three FM-components, depending on the given phase value.

A complete (constantly) changing phase winding corresponds to a (constant) passing through the three plots in Figure 6 from left to right which is then audible as a circular path in terms of sound color. Figure 7 traces the corresponding processes for two selected tone positions

$x = C$ and $x = G$ from the time development of the fifth-deflected ground state for $0 \leq t \leq 3$.

Figure 7: Changing impact of each the three FM-components for the time development of the fifth-deflected ground state at positions $x = C$ (top) and $x = G$ (bottom) for the time span $0 \leq t \leq 3$.

The same idea can be applied to other more recent synthesis methods. In the context of this paper it is particularly attractive to experiment with the *QSynthi* plugin ([5]), because it is inspired by similar methods, namely the usage of one-dimensional Quantum wave functions in the role of the signals themselves, where the configuration space is the time axis.

In addition to the sonification of the phase in these sound color changes in each frequency level we control the loudness of each component by the corresponding magnitude change. In addition there are many further possibilities for refinements. Each of the frequencies can undergo slight modifications which are also controlled by the magnitude of the wave function at corresponding voice position. Likewise, it is possible to influence to modulation frequencies at the individual levels of the overall superposition. For these experiments we use deflections of the excited states as initial states. Both parameters (the index, i.e. the energy level of the excited state as well as the amount of deflection) result in a rich variety of sound continua.

5 Bringing it all together

In our presentation we will first illustrate the variety of musical raw material, which can be obtained by the described experiments. In a second step we will share some combinations from these three sources: basic melody, heterophonic texture and continuous sound processes.

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Figure 8: Comparison of the time development of the deflected ground state (deflected by one fifth) with the time development of the deflected 3rd excited state (deflected by three fifths) in the time range $0 \leq t \leq 3$. The time parameter expands from bottom to top, the voice positions for different frequencies from left to right

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